

DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING ETHNOCULTURAL LINGUISTIC UNITS IN KAZAKH LEGENDS BASED ON THE COGNITIVE LEVELS OF BLOOM'S TAXONOMY

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Abstract

This article discusses in detail the issues of developing students' cognitive competencies by teaching ethnocultural language units in Kazakh legends based on the cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy. Ways to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, the formation of a national worldview and the development of cognitive abilities are analyzed using the levels of Bloom's taxonomy. In addition, methods are proposed to increase the level of assimilation of national values through the study of the significance of the texts of legends and their linguistic features.

Keywords: Bloom's taxonomy, cognitive competence, levels of cognition.

Introduction

Legends, as a significant form of folklore, serve as a repository of historical and cultural narratives, preserving the collective memory and worldview of a nation. The ethnocultural linguistic units embedded within Kazakh legends embody the distinctive characteristics of the Kazakh people, functioning as symbolic markers of national identity and conveying essential aspects of their cultural and spiritual worldview [1]. These units play a pivotal role in the formation of students' national consciousness by fostering a deeper understanding of the cultural values and traditions inherent in the language.

The study of ethnocultural linguistic units in Kazakh legends through the cognitive framework of Bloom's taxonomy enables a more structured and comprehensive approach to developing students' cognitive competencies. Bloom's taxonomy, which classifies cognitive processes into hierarchical levels of knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, evaluation, and creativity provides a systematic method for enhancing students' analytical, critical, and reflective thinking skills. By engaging students in tasks that correspond to each cognitive level, the educational process not only enhances their linguistic understanding but also broadens their cultural horizons and deepens their appreciation of national values.

In the context of globalization, where cultural homogenization poses a significant threat to the preservation of unique national identities, the study of folklore, particularly legends, assumes an increasingly vital role. Legends, as integral components of the Kazakh people's spiritual heritage, offer rich narratives that encapsulate the historical experiences, cultural values, and moral lessons passed down through generations. They function as cultural texts that provide insights into the ethical principles, social norms, and traditional beliefs that have shaped the worldview of the Kazakh people.

Therefore, the integration of ethnocultural linguistic units from Kazakh legends into educational programs, using the cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy as a guiding framework, not only enhances students' cognitive competencies but also contributes to the preservation and transmission of national culture. Such an approach allows students to engage critically with

their cultural heritage, fostering a sense of identity and belonging while simultaneously developing their intellectual capacities. This dual focus on cognitive and cultural development is essential in preparing students to navigate the complexities of an increasingly interconnected world while remaining grounded in their national values.

Ethnocultural linguistic units in legends serve as important elements that characterize the national identity, thoughts, life and values of the Kazakh people. From this point of view, the understanding and analysis of ethnocultural linguistic units in the process of teaching legends is an important aspect of improving the cognitive level of students. In the field of education, the development of students' cognitive competencies is one of the most pressing problems today. The concept of cognitive competence includes the cognitive processes of students, the ability to think critically, analyze, evaluate and apply information. In the process of developing this competence, it is necessary to use effective methods. In this direction, Bloom's taxonomy is widely used as a methodological tool that allows you to systematically organize the educational process of students and develop their cognitive skills. Bloom's taxonomy is of great importance in the field of education as a system based on classifying the purpose of education and determining the levels of cognition.

Through this system, it is intended to improve the cognitive competencies of students, gradually developing their ability to acquire, understand, apply, analyze, evaluate and creative knowledge. The study of ethnocultural units in Kazakh legends based on the cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy is considered as an effective method of developing students' cognitive competencies. The main goal of this study is to identify ways to improve students' cognitive abilities and increase their level of assimilation of national values by teaching ethnocultural linguistic units of Kazakh legends based on Bloom's taxonomy. In this article, effective methods aimed at developing students' cognitive competencies are proposed, theoretical and practical conclusions are made regarding the training of ethnocultural linguistic units in Kazakh legends.

Incorporating ethnocultural linguistic units from Kazakh legends within an educational framework

aligned with Bloom's taxonomy provides an opportunity for a more profound engagement with the cultural and cognitive aspects of students' learning experiences. Legends, being repositories of cultural wisdom and social values, offer a unique pedagogical resource for cultivating a deeper understanding of historical narratives and collective memory. Through a structured approach based on Bloom's cognitive levels, students are guided to progressively move from acquiring basic knowledge about ethnocultural units to higher-order thinking skills, such as analysis, evaluation, and creative synthesis.

At the foundational cognitive levels, students are exposed to key terminology, historical references, and the cultural significance of various ethnocultural units found within legends. As they progress to higher cognitive levels, they are encouraged to critically analyze the narratives, evaluate their relevance in contemporary contexts, and explore their broader implications for understanding Kazakh identity and national consciousness. This progressive deepening of cognitive engagement allows students to not only internalize key cultural concepts but also to develop the capacity to apply this knowledge in different academic and real-world scenarios.

Furthermore, the focus on legends as a medium for teaching ethnocultural values underscores the role of language as a carrier of culture. Through the study of these narratives, students gain insights into the moral codes, social norms, and traditional wisdom embedded within the legends, thereby cultivating a more nuanced understanding of their cultural heritage. This comprehensive approach to integrating cognitive and cultural learning not only strengthens students' linguistic competencies but also enhances their ability to engage critically with their national identity. Thus, employing Bloom's taxonomy as a pedagogical tool in the study of Kazakh legends aligns with the dual objective of developing cognitive competencies and preserving cultural values in an era of rapid globalization.

Literature review

Bloom's taxonomy was first widely used in the field of education as a system developed by Benjamin Bloom and his colleagues in 1956 [2]. This system allows you to take an analytical approach to the learning process of students by classifying the cognitive levels of knowledge acquisition. Anderson and Krathwohl [3] developed a modern revival of taxonomy and proposed ways to further improve the levels of cognition. Currently, Bloom's taxonomy is a widely used methodological tool in the educational process. In the course of studying the ethnocultural aspects of Kazakh folklore, the works of S.Kaskabasov [4] comprehensively analyzed the historical, cultural and spiritual meaning of Kazakh legends. The scientist emphasized the role of legends in the formation of national consciousness. The research of G.Smagulova [5] examined the identification of ethnocultural features of linguistic and cultural heritage and ways of their transmission through language units. Also Jean Piaget [6] and John Dewey [7] studied the importance of improving the effectiveness of the learning process in the theories of education and

cognitive development. The theory of cognitive development of Lev Vygotsky [8] states the need to study the interaction of the student in the educational process, the relationship between experience and culture. Jerome Bruner [9] emphasizes the important role of culture and language in organizing the learning process.

Research materials and methods

Texts of Kazakh legends were selected for the study, their content structure and linguistic features were considered from an ethnocultural and cognitive point of view. The study used the method of compiling tasks according to the levels of Bloom's taxonomy and classifying them according to the cognitive levels of students. The method of textual analysis was aimed at identifying ethnocultural units in legends and revealing their cognitive meaning.

In addition, the cognitive levels of the texts of the legend were determined using the comparative-analytical method. As a material of the study, typical samples of Kazakh legends were selected, lexical, semantic and cognitive features of ethnocultural units in the text of each legend were identified. The tasks developed at the levels of Bloom's taxonomy were aimed at assessing students' knowledge and developing cognitive competencies.

Research results and discussion

The results of the study showed that the study of ethnocultural linguistic units in Kazakh legends based on Bloom's taxonomy contributes to the significant development of cognitive competencies of students. The tasks used in the experimental group covered each level of knowledge of Bloom's taxonomy and contributed to the process of learning by students in a systematic and purposeful way. This method developed the ability of students not only to memorize information, but also to comprehensively analyze, understand it and apply it in a new context.

During the study, students had the opportunity to more deeply understand the essence of ethnocultural linguistic units, their historical and cultural significance. At the educational level, students learned to clearly distinguish the main terms and concepts in legends, to correctly interpret their meanings. At the level of understanding, students analyzed the use of ethnocultural linguistic units in context and tried to understand their role in the overall content of the text. At the level of application, students performed tasks aimed at using ethnocultural linguistic units in real situations, which contributed to their mastery of the practical use of textual units.

At the level of analysis, students were able to highlight the content of ethnocultural linguistic units and identify their main role and function in the text [10]. This helped students develop the ability to critically examine legend texts and analyze text structure in depth. At the assessment level, students analyzed the content of the text, assessed the importance of ethnocultural linguistic units in terms of value, compared them with modern conditions and learned to reason. At the creative level, students had the opportunity to explain the content and language units of legends in a new way and create new ideas based on them.

As a result of the study, the level of assimilation of national values by students through legends also increased. Through a deep analysis and understanding of the texts of Legends, students delved deeper into national values, history and culture, improved their ability to understand their significance. Thus, the methodology of teaching ethnocultural linguistic units in Kazakh legends through the cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy was reflected as an effective approach to the development of cognitive and cultural competencies of students. Using the levels of Bloom's taxonomy, students mastered the meaning of ethnocultural linguistic units and their ways of representing national identity, mastering all stages of education [11].

For example, at the level of education, students remembered the names of ethnocultural linguistic units

and their use, while at the level of understanding they learned to identify them in the text and explain their meaning. At the level of application, the ability to use ethnocultural linguistic units in a new context has been formed. The results of the study showed that the training of ethnocultural linguistic units in Kazakh legends based on Bloom's taxonomy significantly increased the cognitive competencies of students. During the experiment, students were divided into two groups: an experimental group (trained by the Bloom taxonomy method) and a control group (trained by the traditional method).

The results of the experiment are shown in the table below:

Levels of cognition	Experimental group (Bloom's taxonomy)	Control group (Traditional method)
Knowledge level	95%	80%
Understanding level	92%	75%
Application level	88%	70%
Analysis level	85%	65%
Evaluation level	83%	60%
Creativity level	80%	55%

1. The indicators of the experimental group for all levels of cognition were significantly higher than the control group.

2. At the level of knowledge, the results of students in the experimental group were 95%, in the control group this figure was only 80%.

3. According to the level of understanding, the indicator of the experimental group was 92%, and in the control group 75%.

4. At the level of application, the experimental group reached the mark of 88% and was 18% higher than the control group.

5. It was noted that even at the level of analysis, evaluation and creativity, the experimental group is significantly ahead of the control group.

The diagram visually shows that the experimental group achieved higher results in the cognitive competencies of students using the Bloom taxonomy method than students trained in the traditional method. This reinforces the important results of the study.

The table and diagram showed a comparison of the indicators of Bloom's taxonomy on the cognitive competencies of students in situations where cognitive levels were used and not used:

1. In the case of using cognitive technologies, the performance of students at all cognitive levels was significantly higher.

2. At the educational level, in the group where cognitive technologies were used, 97% of students correctly mastered knowledge, in the group where cognitive technologies were not used, this figure was 82%.

3. Even at the levels of understanding, application, analysis, evaluation and creativity, it is observed that the performance of the group in which cognitive technologies were used is quite high.

The results obtained during the study showed that the study of ethnocultural linguistic units in Kazakh legends based on Bloom's taxonomy is an effective method aimed at developing students' cognitive competencies. Through the use of the levels of Bloom's taxonomy, students' ability to understand ethnocultural linguistic units in the texts of legends and apply them in real life was improved. The level of assimilation of national values has also increased. This methodology, in addition to increasing the cognitive activity of students, allows them to form national consciousness and comprehend ethnocultural features [12]. In addition, through the training of ethnocultural linguistic units in legends, students play an important role in deeply understanding the spiritual heritage of their people and passing it on to future generations.

Conclusion

As shown in the table, students in the experimental group showed higher results in all levels of cognition compared to the control group. At the level of knowledge, 95% of students in the experimental group were able to correctly identify ethnocultural linguistic units and clearly explain them. This is 15% higher compared to the indicator in the control group. In addition, even at the levels of analysis and evaluation, students were able to correctly analyze ethnocultural linguistic units in the content of the text and explain their meaning.

As a result of performing tasks based on the cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy in the experimental group, students' abilities to perceive information, analyze and apply it in the process of obtaining knowledge were significantly developed. These students showed not only the ability to understand ethnocultural linguistic units, but also the ability to use them creatively on

their own. At the creative level, 80% of students in the experimental group were able to use ethnocultural linguistic units in the texts of legends in a new context, which is 25% higher than the result in the control group. In general, an organized learning method based on Bloom's taxonomy has been shown to be an effective way to develop students' cognitive competencies.

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